

The Design and Implementation of a Graph-based P2P Data Storage Service

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Abstract

This paper presents the design of G-IDSS (Graph-based InnoCyPES Data Storage Service) a novel distributed data storage service, built around a P2P network overlay to support handling distributed data, accessible through a standard command-line interface and based on a graph database to support schema-less management of distributed data stored among the peers. The mechanisms to facilitate the execution of complex queries requiring distributed data integration and fusion are also presented and discussed. Besides the design, this work also provides relevant details related to the implementation of G-IDSS, reflecting several use-cases demanding data that are distributed across different location, even geographically spread. G-IDSS can accommodate hundreds of peers in an overlay and can scale even further. The tool is able to run distributed queries and to integrate data that are stored in different sources.

Keywords: P2P; large-scale data management; decentralised database; distributed systems; data integration; graph data.

1 Introduction

The amount of data produced is growing at rapid rates from an increasing number of sources [1]. The rate at which the data is currently generated is scaling up in terms of size and number of sources. With an increasing number of connected devices, data can now originate from different geographical locations, different machine types, and can be generated at varied rates. This is largely influenced by the growing number of online interactions, scientific research data, and industrial applications data. Managing this kind of data can be challenging with traditional data management tools [2–4].

Traditionally, data has been managed predominantly through centralised databases and data warehouses, which, despite their advantages in consistency and ease of management, are highly limited in scalability, fault-tolerance, and latency, particularly for geographically distributed or dynamically evolving datasets [5]. Managing modern data effectively in such settings poses considerable challenges. First, scalability becomes increasingly complex due to the large volumes and real-time generation of data. Second, data and systems heterogeneity complicates integration and query execution. Lastly, ensuring consistency, availability, and partition tolerance simultaneously is exceptionally challenging (as shown by the CAP theorem) even when data is placed in distributed environments [6].

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The prevailing data trends and management requirements demand innovative approaches to data management [7], particularly approaches that allow both horizontal and vertical scaling [8–10]. This would allow systems to manage colossal data whilst also offering a simplified approach for data retrieval. An exploration of P2P (Peer to Peer) systems [11–15] (for data management and beyond), given their features, is considered one of the preferred choice towards the management of large-scale systems.

This paper presents a distributed data management system based on a P2P overlay and a graph database [16]. The combination is also associated with its data querying approach, which is appropriate for distributed settings. The combination of these tools enables efficient data querying and storage across multiple distributed peers, ensuring comprehensive data coverage and fault tolerance while balancing the computational load of the peers. This is achieved through a unique and innovative approach to managing distributed queries in a resource-constrained environment.

The main contributions of this paper lie in the methods for decentralised graph data management, data querying, and their integration, which are facilitated by a DHT (Distributed Hash Table) overlay. The approach to executing distributed queries in a P2P system is demonstrated by illustrating query propagation and how to limit continuous broadcasting. Due to the limitations of the query language implemented, the study shows alternative query parsing strategies to support some of the important queries that could potentially facilitate the retrieval of useful reports.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 recalls the underlying technologies and the state-of-the-art practices. Section 3 presents the design and implementation of the model for graph-based P2P data management. The validation of the proposed functionalities is presented in Section 4. Lastly, conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2 Background and Literature Review

2.1 Background

P2P systems are an important piece of technology for decentralised computing, and are praised for their scalability, resilience, and ability to operate without a centralised infrastructure [17]. They have been widely adopted for file sharing, content distribution, and blockchain technology. Primarily, P2P architectures distribute workload across nodes, for the goal of enhancing efficiency and fault-tolerance. Here, we highlight primary known applications of P2P systems allowing proper case building, summarise commonly known architecture to justify our choices for the adopted architecture, and finally, hint at opportunities for exploration within P2P systems.

P2P systems gained initial prominence through file-sharing applications such as Napster [18], Gnutella [19], and BitTorrent [20]. Napster’s centralised index facilitated music sharing, demonstrating P2P’s potential for rapid content dissemination. Gnutella’s decentralised protocol improved scalability via flooding-based queries [21], whilst BitTorrent’s tit-for-tat mechanism and piecewise distribution achieved high throughput, reportedly driving significant Internet traffic in the 2000s [22]. Beyond file sharing, systems like Skype leveraged P2P for voice-over-IP services, ensuring strong connectivity [23], and blockchain platforms like Bitcoin and Ethereum utilised P2P networks for decentralised transaction validation, achieving global adoption through cryptographic security and consensus protocols [24, 25]. To date, the success of P2P systems originates from their scalability, fault-tolerance, and adaptability, enabled by distributed resource utilisation and dynamic routing mechanisms like Kademlia [26].

Despite challenges such as free-riding and security vulnerabilities, innovations in incentive models and secure protocols have sustained their relevance. These attributes have made P2P systems foundational to applications like decentralised storage (e.g., IPFS - InterPlanetary File System) and computing, positioning them as a critical paradigm in distributed systems research.

2.2 P2P Architectures

Most P2P systems share the following common characteristics: resource sharing, decentralisation, symmetry, autonomy, self-organisation, scalability and stability, hence being widely adopted. Several designs have led to various proposals for P2P network classification. For example, file-sharing systems have been categorised into generations. First generation are hybrid designs that combine servers with P2P routing, and the second generation are based on decentralised architectures. The third generation includes anonymised P2P systems such as Freenet and I2P [17].

However, this kind of classification is not suitable because it overlooks several aspects of P2P systems. Hence, the preferred approach is to classify P2P into structured and unstructured overlays [17, 27]. Unstructured overlays are generally distinguished by how search requests are propagated, distribution of node degree in the peer population, and by differences in link formation with neighbour peers [28]. Structured overlays are differentiated according to the number of hops (i.e., multi-hop, single-hop or variable-hop), routing algorithms, node degree, size of overlay, overlay geometry and lookup type [29]. Structured overlays maintain a deterministic network topology, often utilising mechanisms such as DHTs to ensure predictable lookup paths and efficient routing [30]. In contrast, unstructured overlays rely on probabilistic routing without predefined paths, typically resulting in simpler management but potentially lower efficiency in data retrieval [27]. Structured overlays are chosen for their predictability, scalability, and improved performance in query processing, making them suitable for robust and efficient distributed data management [31]. Other classifications that may not necessarily fall into either structured or unstructured overlays are then categorised into hierarchical, federated, and several different categories, grouped according to service or functionality [29].

2.3 P2P Data Management

Data management has been thoroughly explored, with relational databases dominating the market [32]. Due to their limitations, including their strict rules, there has been a growing interest in other approaches to address challenges related to relational databases. Initially, data warehouses and data lakes were the go-to options in cases where relational databases failed [33, 34]. Recently, NoSQL (Not Only SQL) databases have gained popularity due to their flexibility and support for scalability. NoSQL databases can be classified into four major categories: (i) document-based, (ii) key-value based, (iii) graph-based and (iv) column-based [35]. Among these, graph-based databases naturally represent real-world objects and offer better flexibility and scalability than relational ones. They also partially support ACID (Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation and Durability) properties.

P2P data management systems, on the other hand, represent a decentralised approach for the storage, querying, and sharing of data across multiple peers without a central server [36, 37]. Early P2P systems such as Gnutella and BitTorrent demonstrated the efficiency and scalability of decentralised architectures for file sharing [19–21, 28]. However, their simplistic search mechanisms limited their applicability. Consequently, the development of structured P2P overlays (DHTs) marked a significant advancement. These overlays efficiently handle data lookup, insertion, and retrieval operations with a logarithmic time complexity, thereby enabling more sophisticated data management tasks [26, 30, 38]. Nevertheless, DHT-based approaches typically support only key-value storage, restricting their suitability for complex queries involving multidimensional or relational data.

To overcome this limitation, researchers have developed advanced P2P data management solutions that combine structured overlays with richer data representations. For instance, P-Grid [39], XPeer [40], PORDaS [41], OrbitDB2 [42], peerbit [43], DefraDB [44] and PeerDB [45] are dominant examples that integrate structured overlay protocols with database functionalities, enabling sophisticated queries and flexible data schemas in decentralised environments.

Other advanced approaches extend further into graph-based data models, recognising that real-world datasets are often naturally represented as graphs. Systems such as HypergraphDB [46], GUN [47], and Neo4j (with decentralisation extensions) demonstrate significant improvements in handling graph-based queries and managing highly connected and dynamic data efficiently across decentralised networks. We summarise graph-based P2P data management systems in Table 1.

Table 1: Graph-based P2P data management tools

Tool	Main features	Limits
HypergraphDB	Built on hypergraphs and hyperedges to support knowledge presentation and complex data relationships	Not fully decentralised and is also limited to its own query language
GUN	Decentralised graph database engine, supporting flexible data modelling	Does not implement querying mechanisms, but relies on filtering, and key-based access. Full text search is also not possible

However, despite these advances, significant challenges still remain. Issues such as consistency, fault tolerance, efficient query processing, data integration, and distributed transactions in dynamic and potentially unreliable P2P networks continue to attract research attention. HypergraphDB, for instance, was designed as an embedded, transactional database relying on BerkeleyDB for low-level storage, which is inherently centralised [46]. HypergraphDB also lacks native support for horizontal scalability and distributed clusters, necessitating a custom solution to manage large-scale, distributed hypergraphs. Furthermore, support for query distribution is highly limited.

Similar challenges are experienced with PeerDB. It is designed to support centralised replication and hence experiences limited horizontal scalability [45]. P-Grid provides comprehensive support for P2P overlay extending from traditional structured overlays, but gives no support for typical database management functionalities [39]. GUN has demonstrated an innovative approach to mapping complex data relationships; its querying mechanisms do not entirely align with the existing database infrastructure [47]. In this regard, future research directions include developing an efficient distributed query management through optimisation techniques that work towards enhancing security and privacy mechanisms, and creating adaptive data integration strategies. These efforts aim to enhance data availability, usability, and reliability across large-scale P2P systems. This research investigates the feasibility of integrating a P2P overlay with a graph database management system (DBMS) to facilitate efficient distributed query execution and data integration across multiple sources, thereby addressing common existing challenges.

3 Proposed model and Implementation

3.1 Overview of IDSS

This study adopts our P2P data querying and integration strategy named IDSS (InnoCyPES Data Storage Service) originally proposed in [48], which is also briefly described below. The IDSS design presents an innovative approach to managing and integrating distributed data sources. The architecture is primarily designed around a P2P architecture, employing a structured overlay network approach. An overlay utilises a DHT model to ensure effective routing of queries and efficient management of network nodes/peers. The design aims to effectively

Figure 1: Results collection and merging strategy (see [48]).

mitigate single points of failure by distributing data storage across multiple nodes, and hence, significantly enhancing system/data availability, resilience, and scalability. To improve its efficiency for database management in a decentralised environment, IDSS uses an embedded database engine since using a stand-alone database server introduces another point of failure and also requires, for each local query to be issued at a peer, a client-server network interaction accounting for precious time. The architecture integrates three major components: (i) an interface for query submission, (ii) a data management layer that comprises a query and update manager, and (iii) a P2P overlay with DHT as presented in Figure 3. This design also reduces the complexity and improves the overall reliability of the system.

The query management aspect in the IDSS is designed to consider that there will be several peers in the overlay, each hosting its own local database. These peers will also act as data storage locations, and there will be clients which submits queries to these data storage points servers. A client submitting queries to an overlay can be either part of the overlay (i.e. a peer) or it can be a stand-alone client connecting to one of the peers that belongs to the overlay. A client submits queries asynchronously to any network node (referred as an initiator node), with each query being uniquely identified across the entire network by a Uniform Query Identifier (UQI). Queries propagate through structured broadcasting (by utilising DHT), efficiently reaching all relevant nodes (referred to as intermediate nodes) without duplication. Each node executes the query locally, with results being aggregated not using a centralised merging at the initiating node (Figure 1a) but through distributed merging across multiple nodes following a tree structure (Figure 1b), in order to balance the computational load among the peers. For fully decentralised functionality of the storage service, it is recommended that aggregation and results merging be distributed across multiple nodes to avoid overloading an initiator node with results processing.

To efficiently manage the queries in an overlay, the IDSS design uses several query states. When a query is submitted to a peer, it is labelled with a QUEUED state. When the query is executed locally, the state changes to LOCALLY_EXECUTED, before a peer forwards it to the peers in its routing table ¹. Each intermediate peer, after running the query locally, forwards the query to the peers in its routing table. It then collects the results and merges the aggregate result. After this step, an intermediate peer changes the query state to COMPLETED, after

¹A routing table is a structured list of known peers maintained by a node to efficiently locate other peers or content in the network, typically using a DHT

Figure 2: Query states (see [48]).

which the results are sent back to the parent peer from which the query was received, and the query state is changed to `SENT_BACK`, as shown in Figure 2a. For an initiator node, the same protocol will be followed, except that the query will not be set to the `SENT_BACK` state after completion because an initiator node received a query from a client, which is not involved in query broadcasting; rather, the client expects to retrieve the final result of its query when connecting later providing the query’s UQI. Hence, the query state in the initiator node must be set to `COMPLETED`, as depicted in Figure 2b. This stage can be reached in two ways, (i) when all results has been collected or (ii) when the user’s defined Time-To-Live (TTL) has elapsed. It is also possible for the two conditions to occur concurrently. A TTL parameter is incorporated to balance query response time and the completeness of returned results, ensuring both performance and reliability. TTL is introduced to further control how long the query should be processed, without which, given an extremely large number of peers involved in an overlay, a query is likely to require too much time.

The current implementation retains the original IDSS design, as described in this subsection, for peer overlay structure and query management. The technical implementation, including tools, techniques, and the reasons for selecting the technology stack, is further described below.

3.2 P2P Overlay

The current design utilises a structured P2P overlay network built using the `libp2p`² library, along with its Go implementation, to enable decentralised communication and data distribution. The Golang implementation was chosen because it is currently the most complete among others within `libp2p`.

`Libp2p` is open-source and provides full-stack protocols for P2P systems, bringing a simplified approach to the implementation of large-scale P2P systems (whose development has always been complex and challenging for many years). It is built on top of IPFS, providing new applications with state-of-the-art P2P capabilities, including the flexibility to choose specific network features, interoperability, and enabling decentralised infrastructure, even for non-distributed projects. The overlay forms a structured P2P network, where peers (nodes) communicate directly without a central coordinator.

²<https://libp2p.io/>

Figure 3: G-IDSS P2P Data Storage Reference Architecture

With libp2p, each node in the system initially initialises as a libp2p host that generates a unique cryptographic identity and dynamically allocates network addresses (multiaddresses), providing a unique identification of each peer in the overlay. A node’s multiaddress is formed by several segments, which, when concatenated, represent a self-describing hierarchical address format enabling peers to establish connections among each other. These addresses are defined in the following format:

`/ip4/127.0.0.1/tcp/4000/p2p/QmXyzbc456...`

- **/ip4/127.0.0.1** - This part specifies the network protocol (IPv4) and the IP address of the node. It specifies the protocol and corresponding address at which the node is reachable. Other supported alternatives include (IPv6)/ip6, /dns/, /dns4/, or /dns6/, which allow to resolve hostnames to their respective IP addresses;
- **/tcp/4000** - This indicates that the node is using the TCP transport protocol and is listening on port 4000. The transport layer ensures the reliable and ordered delivery of messages between peers. Other alternatives include UDP (/udp/), which is useful for lower latency but may be less reliable and QUIC (/quic/), which provides connection-oriented reliability on top of UDP. For browser or web-based applications, WebSockets (/ws/) and secure WebSockets (/wss/) are also supported;
- **/p2p/QmXyzbc456...** - The /p2p (formerly /ipfs in earlier versions) prefix identifies that the following string is the unique Peer ID of the node. This identifier is generated using cryptographic keys and distinguishes the node within the P2P overlay network.

The core component of the overlay is a Kademlia DHT, which provides scalable peer discovery, routing, and content addressing [26]. The Kademlia DHT organises peers in a binary tree structure based on their peer IDs, using an XOR-based distance metric to determine proximity between nodes. With Kademlia DHT, a bootstrap process continually maintains a healthy and up-to-date routing table. The bootstrap process runs once on startup, and then periodically (the time interval can be set) to discover new joining peers and determine peers that are close to oneself. Specifically, the G-IDSS leverages the DHT to facilitate efficient key-based routing and peer discovery, with additional local discovery enabled by multicast DNS (mDNS). This allows the G-IDSS to run both locally (using local and custom bootstrap nodes) and globally (utilising default bootstrap peers provided by libp2p). The discovery and content advertising process of the G-IDSS benefits from the custom-defined G-IDSS service tag, defined during peer node initialisation.

To control the propagation of messages in the overlay, libp2p supports the addition of a specific protocol prefix in the protocol ID. The G-IDSS applies its own “idss/” prefix. For instance, the G-IDSS’s protocol used across an overlay becomes /idss/kad/1.0.0 for global connection or /idss/lan/kad/1.0.0 for local connection instead of the generalised protocol IDs /kad/1.0.0 or /lan/kad/1.0.0. This approach allows for dynamic peer connectivity and controlled population of the DHT. In this regard, only peers that recognise and support the G-IDSS protocol can participate in the exchange of messages. This avoids conflicts with other protocols operating over the same network, helps in organising and routing messages correctly, and facilitates future upgrades or changes without interfering with other network communications. It is particularly important when the G-IDSS is launched to the public internet, where the need for packet filtration is of even greater importance. Hence, key libp2p features implemented in the G-IDSS can be summarised as follows:

- *Multiaddress support and peer identification* - each node is assigned a unique cryptographic identity during initialisation, ensuring that every peer can be uniquely and securely identified within the network. This is accompanied by a self-describing multiaddress format allowing identification of various network protocols;
- *Secure communication* - libp2p integrates either TLS (Transport Layer Security) or the Noise security protocol to encrypt communications among the peers. This guarantees confidentiality and integrity of the transmitted data. The G-IDSS applies the Noise protocol because it is lighter than TLS, also flexible, and easy to embed in a P2P setup without relying on a complex PKI infrastructure. Requirements that align well with a decentralised system;
- *Stream multiplexing* - multiple logical streams can be carried over a single physical connection. This feature allows concurrent communication channels among peers, improving overall network efficiency. In the G-IDSS, this also ensures reliable query propagation and data transfer by integrating it with the protocol buffer (protobuf)³ for data serialisation;
- *Local peer discovery* - mDNS enables automatic discovery of peers on local networks without the need for centralised DNS servers, which facilitates rapid bootstrapping of nodes. Additionally, support is also available for the bootstrap and random walk protocols;
- *Efficient peer discovery and bootstrapping* - the Kademlia DHT facilitates finding and connecting to other peers through a decentralised routing mechanism. It supports bootstrapping through a list of known peers (for global discovery) and continuously discovers new joining peers. For local discovery, the mDNS service is used to connect to peers that broadcast with the same service name, thereby populating its routing table. In this case, to form an overlay, there must exist at least two peers. In the G-IDSS, DHT also facilitates efficient query propagation and routing;
- *Key-based routing* - messages are routed based on keys in a deterministic manner. This ensures that any message addressed to a given key is incrementally forwarded toward the destination node;
- *Scalability* - by organising peers into a structured overlay, the DHT supports scalable and efficient lookups. The routing table is maintained in a way that balances the load and minimises the latency;
- *Periodic Routing Table refresh* - the DHT periodically refreshes its routing table to account for peer churning (nodes joining or leaving), which ensures that the routing information remains current and reliable. The G-IDSS maintains its routing table, which is refreshed

³<https://protobuf.dev/>

by default hourly (the refresh rate can be adjusted according to requirements), and tracks overlay metrics such as latency and success rates through periodic pings.

3.3 Database Management System

The G-IDSS integrates EliasDB⁴, a Golang graph-based database to manage data and query information. EliasDB is a lightweight solution for projects having data that demands a graph structure and provides most functionalities without the need for a third-party application. It is a disk-based graph database used for storing both application data and metadata related to queries. This tool facilitates the representation of complex relationships by modelling data as nodes and edges. It defines a storage file in a disk which can contain a fixed size of records, each with a unique identifier. On disk the logical Storage File is split into multiple files each with a maximum file size of 10 gigabyte. G-IDSS maintains a unique database instance in a peer-specific directory, which is available on each peer.

Data can be stored and retrieved using the GraphQL interface and EliasDB's own query language, EQL, for more complex queries with an SQL-like syntax. For robust applications, the embedded EliasDB supports transactions with rollback, iteration of data and rule-based consistency management. To benefit from the rich set of features offered by EliasDB, G-IDSS utilised EQL for graph traversal and data querying, while employing specific ECAL (Event Condition Action Language) functions (encompassing transactions) for node or edge creation, updates, and deletions.

The graph database is initialised during peer startup and leverages a predefined graph data structure defined in a JSON file. The format enables easy mapping of nodes and edges along with their associated properties. The examples in this work will follow a snapshot of the data schema described in Figure 4. The choice of EliasDB is justified by its lightweight footprint, embedded architecture, and high performance for graph operations, which eliminates the need for external database servers and reduces latency in a distributed environment. Its straightforward API and EQL's similarity to SQL further simplify integration with a P2P system.

To facilitate testing, G-IDSS includes a data generation mechanism implemented in a Python script, `generate_data.py`. This script, when invoked, generates synthetic graph data including client nodes, consumption nodes, and edges linking clients to consumption records. The data is serialised as JSON and then loaded into EliasDB, with transactions ensuring consistency. The Python Faker⁵ library ensures realistic data generation, whilst configurable parameters allow adjusting the data volume to be generated.

This approach enables rapid prototyping and validation of query execution without reliance on real-world datasets, with JSON's portability simplifying integration with EliasDB. In the defined graph model, the Client node has 5 properties: key, kind, name, contract number and power of the house, as detailed in Table 2. The consumption node holds 4 properties: key, kind, timestamp and measurement, as detailed in Table 3. The data model also contains edges to connect the two nodes, allocating each consumption record to a household as described in Table 4. The number of nodes or edges to be generated can be changed using the available `generate_data.py` script. Hence, the data querying examples in the following sections will be based on this data schema.

3.4 Query Management

We recall that a client peer must connect to one of the peers in the overlay to submit queries. Once a query is submitted, it is then handled according to the description in Section 3.1. To facilitate efficient query propagation and result aggregation in a distributed graph database

⁴<https://github.com/krotik/eliasdb>

⁵<https://faker.readthedocs.io/en/master/>

```

"nodes": [
  {
    "kind": "node1",
    "key": 1,
    "property1": "value1",
    "property2": "value2",
    "property3": "value3"
  },
  {
    "kind": "node2",
    "key": 14,
    "property1": "value1",
    "property2": "value2"
  }
],
"edges": [
  {
    "key": "e1",
    "kind": "my_kind",
    "end1key": 1,
    "end1kind": "node1",
    "end1role": "role1",
    "end1cascading": true,
    "end2key": 14,
    "end2kind": "node2",
    "end2role": "role2",
    "end2cascading": true
  }
]

```

Figure 4: JSON mapping for nodes and edges

Table 2: Client’s node properties description

Property	Type	Sample	Description
Key	Integer	10	Unique ID for the client node
Kind	String	Client	Type of the node (always Client)
Name	String	John	Name of the client
Contract No.	Integer	6831	Client’s contract number
Power	Integer	798	Power capacity of the household

system, we define a protobuf schema using the proto3 syntax, encapsulated within the common G-IDSS package. This schema provides a lightweight, platform-agnostic mechanism for serialising and exchanging structured messages across network nodes. The schema comprises three primary message types: QueryMessage, QueryState, and Row, alongside an enumeration

Table 3: Consumption’s node properties description

Property	Type	Sample	Description
Key	Integer	11	Unique ID for the node
Kind	String	Consumption	Type of the node
Timestamp	Integer	1625133600	UNIX timestamp
Measurement	Integer	7688529	Power capacity

Table 4: Client-Consumption Edge properties description

Property	Type	Sample	Description
Key	String	e345	Unique ID for the edge
Kind	String	belongs_to	Relationship type
end1key	Integer	10	Key of the source node (Client)
end1kind	String	Client	Type of the source node
end1role	String	Owner	Role of the source node in the relationship
end1cascading	Boolean	True	Whether changes cascade from end1 to the relationship
end2key	Integer	11	Key of the target node (Consumption).
end2kind	String	Consumption	Type of the target node (always "Consumption").
end2role	String	Usage	Role of the target node
end2cascading	Boolean	True	Whether changes cascade from end2 to the relationship.

MessageType to distinguish between query and result messages.

The QueryMessage message serves as the core structure for encapsulating query-related information propagated through the network. It includes fields for the message type (type, is an enum of QUERY or RESULT), the query string (query), a unique query identifier (uqid), and a timestamp (timestamp). Additional fields manage the query’s lifecycle and metadata, such as time-to-live (ttl, a float indicating the query’s propagation duration), sender and originator peer identifiers (sender and originator), and an error message (error) for failure reporting. The labels field, a repeated string, enables categorisation of queries, while the result field, a repeated Row message, stores query results. The record_count field tracks the number of records in the result, and the state field, of type QueryState, captures the query’s execution status.

The QueryState message defines the state of a query within the distributed system, using an embedded enumeration State with values:

- QUEUED (query available in the queue);
- LOCALLY_EXECUTED (query executed locally);
- SENT_BACK (result returned to the parent node);
- COMPLETED (query fully processed);
- FAILED (query execution failed).

The QueryState message also includes an optional result field and a repeated Row to store intermediate or final results during query processing.

The Row message represents a single row in a query result, with a repeated data field of strings to accommodate flexible, schema-agnostic data representation. This design ensures compatibility with diverse query result formats whilst maintaining simplicity. Similarly, the presented Protobuf schema enables robust, scalable communication in the distributed graph database system by providing a standardised, efficient format for query propagation, state tracking, and result aggregation. Its use of enumerations and repeated fields aims to support extensibility and adaptability to different query workloads, thereby making the tool reliable in performance in a decentralised network environment.

3.5 Client Implementation

The G-IDSS client provides a command-line interface for interacting with the P2P network. The client connects to a peer using a specified multiaddress and protocol (which is /lan/kad/1.0.0 by default), submitting queries as QueryMessage objects over libp2p streams. The user inputs a query and TTL value, with responses deserialised from protobuf and saved to XML files (results/<uqid>.xml) for persistence. The client distinguishes between status messages (e.g., for inserting data) and query results, logging relevant details. Termination signals are handled gracefully by cleaning up result files and closing the libp2p host, ensuring the testing environment remains clean during the testing phase. This lightweight client design ensures accessibility while maintaining compatibility with the server’s architecture, with XML output facilitating integration with external tools, in case the tool has to be integrated with other systems.

4 Validation

To evaluate the performance, scalability, and data integration of the G-IDSS, a series of experiments were designed to validate its core components: P2P overlay, peer communication, DBMS, data querying mechanisms, and data integration. This section outlines the experimental setup, the types of experiments conducted, and specific validation strategies for each component, focusing on peer communication, overlay maintenance, database operations, query execution and effectiveness, and data integration for each operation.

4.1 Experimental Setup

Experiments were conducted on various scales to validate the prototype as a proof of concept. Three main testing setups were used based on the required experiments and computing power. The first setup involved a basic GitHub Codespace with 8 GB of memory, 2 Intel(R) Xeon(R) Platinum 8370C CPUs at 2.80 GHz, and 32 GB of disk space, which is referred to as the codespace from now on. The second setup involved a virtual machine on a PC with 32 GB of RAM, an 11th-generation Intel Core i7-10710U CPU at 1.10 GHz, and 500 GB of SSD storage. The VM instance was based on Windows Subsystem for Linux (WSL) running Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS, with 16 GB of memory and 12 logical processors, which we will now refer to as WSL. The third setup involved a server machine running Ubuntu 24.04.2 LTS, with 2 Intel(R) Xeon(R) 12 cores CPUs at 2.00 GHz, 64 GB of memory, and 3 TB of disk space, referred to as the server from now on. The codebase for the prototype is primarily implemented using Go (version 1.21), for P2P overlay and database functionalities. A bash script was used to simulate peers on an overlay, python3 was used to generate synthetic data to populate graph storage. Protobuf was used in the implementation to facilitate stream communication between peers and message serialisation.

The experiments were conducted by running several servers and clients, with each server hosting its own dataset storage. Clients were run in different fashions to test the server’s ability to handle multiple client requests and respond accordingly. During experiments, the number of peers varied from 10 to 1500 to assess for system’s scalability, with each peer running an instance of the EliasDB graph database and the libp2p-based P2P stack. Synthetic data populated each peer’s database with 10 Client nodes, 100 Consumption nodes, and 1000 belongs_to edges, unless specified otherwise in experiments where we tested for scalability. In such scenarios, we generated two graph nodes for each peer, allowing the experiment to allocate compute resources to accommodate an increasing number of peers, rather than allocating compute resources for synthetic data generation. The Kademlia DHT was initialised with a subset of peers as bootstrap nodes, and the Noise protocol ensured secure communication among peers. Performance metrics were collected using the built-in pprof server (localhost:6060) and custom logging (go-log/v2). Each experiment was repeated several times to build concrete conclusions.

4.2 P2P Overlay

In this experiment, the study primarily focused on two key metrics: peer communication and its scalability. In peer communication, during all experiments, peers were able to efficiently create their IDs and overlay properties and then join the G-IDSS overlay (which is launched with its own service tag and protocol). The number of peers during experiments was 10 to 100 peers in the codespace, 200 peers in WSL and 1500 peers in the server. Other similar experiments using IPFS DHT with Go-libp2p reportedly enabled the launch of up to 1000 concurrent peer connections, after which streams were automatically reset. Some libp2p implementations written in Rust reported that nodes can maintain up to 10,000 peer connections, including more than 1500 validator connections ⁶. This implies that scaling to 100000 nodes is viable if the per-node peer degrees remain around 100 connections. It is worth noting that the limited computational resources can limit scalability when experimenting with P2P overlays on a single machine. However, with peer discovery mechanisms (mDNS, DHT, and Bootstrap nodes), scalability can be further enriched because peers are not required to maintain a full connection to each other.

In our experiments, the observed limits on the number of peers that we launched were due to resource exhaustion during the launch process. This improves if the launch process is done in chunks, especially when launching more than 1000 peers. The maintenance of an overlay does not require high computational resources, mainly because we have set the routing table to refresh once every hour, and each peer does not maintain full connection with all peers in the overlay. Libp2p also maintains a bucket size of 20 peers in the routing table, which is configurable depending on the requirements. This means that the computing required increases depending on DHT configurations. Important parameters to consider in such scenarios include the number of peers in the overlay, periodic discovery, routing table updates, liveness checks, handling new connections, and necessary data exchange during overlay population. Furthermore, since the encryption of communication is a requirement, key exchange operations should also be considered.

The observed failures were also due to the synthetic data generation process, rather than peer communication itself. This is the case in our experiments because, for a peer to join an overlay, we require them to have a graph data manager and some data loaded into it, which can be a slightly slower process depending on data size. Hence, to test for the highest number possible that we could launch, we had to set synthetic data generation to the minimum number of nodes and edges possible.

⁶<https://github.com/libp2p/rust-libp2p/discussions/3840?utm>

Table 5: Description of sample queries using the COUNT function

Query	Description
get Client where @count(owner: belongs_to: usage: Consumption) > 4	Returns a list of clients having at least 4 consumption records
get Consumption where @count(:::) > 0	Returns all consumption records that is being connected to any other node. Based on our data model, all consumption records will be returned
get Client where Power > 150 and @count(owner: belongs_to: usage: Consumption) > 5	Returns all clients having at least 5 consumption records and the power of the house should be above 150

4.3 Database Management and Data Querying

This experiment aimed to test the tool’s capabilities for data management in terms of querying and integration in a decentralised fashion. For convenience, experiments on data querying and integration were conducted with 10-100 peers, comprising 10 to 1 million graph nodes, to prove that decentralised graph data can be queried and integrated in a common format.

Each peer joining an overlay is mandated to host a graph DBMS before joining the network. Given the number of peers, this was successful in all experiments, and all peers involved in testing had both DBMS and graph data loaded. The results described in this section are based on query performance in the context of P2P distributed databases.

The G-IDSS implements all basic queries supported by EQL’s syntax. Since their retrieval patterns involve fetching nodes under conditions like = , != , | < , > |, contains, like and arithmetic operators, running such queries in distributed environments requires simple data aggregation methods among peers. Example queries may include:

- get Client
- get Consumption traverse ::: where name = "Alice"
- lookup Client '3' traverse :::
- get Client traverse owner: belongs_to: usage: Consumption
- get Client show name

The traversal expressions indicated by ::: provide a way to traverse the edges to fetch nodes and edges that are connected to each other (an equivalence to relationships in relational databases). The traversal statements may be followed by relational operators to filter data nodes/edges that comply with a condition given, i.e.:

get Client traverse owner: belongs_to: usage: Consumption where measurement >= 300 and measurement <= 800.

The EQL comes with the built-in COUNT function, which can be useful in data querying. For instance, it can be used to fetch nodes which have a certain number of connections (relationships). In this regard, when the count number is set to greater than zero, the query returns all nodes in the graph that are connected to each other and have at least one connection, so any connected node will be returned. Possible queries are presented in Table 5.

When such queries are run in a distributed fashion, they require only result aggregation among peers. However, this is not the case when performing queries that include additional

functions such as sorting datasets or computing the average of data values in a distributed manner. The G-IDSS supports distributed sorting of results using built-in EQL capabilities. To sort data, EQL uses the WITH clause, followed by the ordering command, for which a query has to specify an ascending or descending directive, followed by a property to which you want to refer for sorting, as indicated below. EQL also allows the use of show command to return only a specified property/column.

- get Client with ordering(ascending Client:name)
- get Client show name with ordering(ascending name)

We run test queries by launching up to 100 peers, each having a varied number of graph nodes. We chose two cases which can basically represent a minimal and reasonably high number of graph nodes that can be fetched in a decentralised fashion, as summarised below:

- Case 1: Few peers with huge data load. This is conducted with an experiment launching 10 peers with a huge dataset consisting of 100,000 client nodes, 1,000,000 consumption nodes, and 1,000,000 edges across the entire overlay.
- Case 2: Increased number of peers with a few data. This is conducted by launching 100 peers with 1,000 client nodes, 10,000 consumption nodes, and 10,000 edges across the entire overlay.

The two scenarios will presumably generalise the complexities of data fetching in a few-peer environment and an increased number of peers environment, demonstrating the impact of querying complexities in a scaling network. Three basic queries were considered based on the nature of the result set they return. First, get Client, second, get Consumption, and third, get Consumption traverse ::: These queries present aggregated data based on data integration across peers and traversing across nodes, representing decentralised querying across traversed data. All peers and data generation were initiated by the prepared bash script to automate repeating tasks in the background. With a single client launched, we were able to test all query types described in this section.

The first case query was able to fetch all results in a few seconds, whereas the second case required more time due to the increased number of hops to be performed in the overlay. The time spent in fetching the complete result set is not constant. It is affected by other factors, such as network traffic, the number of concurrent operations that a single server needs to handle, the overlay network size, and others. The TTL set has a high impact on the completeness of the results. A higher TTL value will always guarantee the completeness of results. In small networks and controlled overlays, TTL may not be relevant; however, when running in large networks or querying a global-scale network, TTL becomes relevant. In this case, we also note that the type of queries submitted did not put a significant load on the computation required in comparison to other conditions. However, query formulation remains an important aspect to consider when huge loads are expected.

We also conduct small-scale tests to observe the impact of the TTL value on querying. We run the test by launching 50 peers, each with 10 client nodes (resulting in 500 clients in the overlay), 100 consumption records (resulting in 5,000 consumption records in the overlay), and 5,000 edges (each client node having 100 edges, representing direct connections to consumption records). A query get Client, 3, with 3 representing the TTL, returned a total of 330 records, indicating that 33 out of 50 peers were successfully reached and returned the results. Running the same query with an increased TTL value of 6, i.e., get Client, 6), the G-IDSS was able to fetch all 500 client nodes, thereby reaching all peers in the overlay. Query traversal can also be run in the G-IDSS, specifically to search targeted records. For instance, the query traversal get Client traverse owner: belongs_to: usage: Consumption, 7 retrieves all client records with their

associated consumption records in 7 seconds. i.e., these are two nodes connected through an edge with a connection pattern described as `owner: belongs_to: usage: Consumption`. A detailed description of submitted queries and fetched results is provided in the GitHub repository.

As stated in [48], fetching results in the G-IDSS is based on a “best effort” approach, considering the potentially huge number of distributed servers. Considering other factors that may affect an overlay, querying with TTL 3, for instance, will not always return the same number of records, given a constant number of peers.

G-IDSS also supports running local queries — i.e., queries that are not intended to be broadcast in the overlay. This allows fetching data exclusively from an individual peer, without necessarily fetching data from other peers. Additionally, all operations that require modifications to the graph data are limited to local data repositories, as it would not be reasonable to allow a peer to modify another peer’s datasets. To run local queries, a client must submit a query with either `-l` or `-local` flag. With the current release, we do not necessarily need to submit a TTL, as it is intended to control query propagation and dictate how long a client can wait before receiving the results.

EQL does not inherently support data modification queries; however, EliasDB has built-in ECAL functions for data modifications, which can be executed as EliasDB’s graph manager operations or transactions. These functions are `StoreNode()` for adding a node, `RemoveNode()` for removing a node, and `UpdateNode()` for updating an existing node. The G-IDSS uses custom-defined keywords to facilitate the utilisation of these functions.

To add graph nodes, the G-IDSS uses a keyword `add` to refer to a query that requires the addition of a node. The query must adhere to the “`add <kind> <key> [properties]`” syntax. This can be run as `add Client 14 client_name= "John Doe" contract_number= 7437643 power= 7575`.

To update/modify a graph node, the G-IDSS uses the `update` keyword to change the values of an attribute/property in a graph. For instance, updating the Client with key "14", to a different name, we run the following query: `update Client 14 client_name="John Rhobi"`. Lastly, to delete a graph node a client must use the `delete` keyword, followed by a graph kind and key in the following format: `delete <kind> <key>`. For example, a sample query can be formulated as `delete Client 14`.

In adding and updating graph nodes, queries may include attributes/properties that were not initially available in the graph data model. This implies that when fetching the entire dataset, some graph nodes may have *nil* properties in certain instances, unless the data is universally updated or initial data preprocessing is performed within the G-IDSS.

4.4 G-IDSS Clients

To assess the scalability and reliability of the G-IDSS in a multi-client scenario, an experiment was conducted in which multiple G-IDSS clients were connected to a network of 10 server peers, with each client establishing a connection to a distinct server. The experiment aimed to evaluate the system’s performance in terms of connection establishment and data querying, focusing on success rates and data querying. The setup deployed 10 server peers, each running as a separate process with a unique TCP port (`/ip4/127.0.0.1/tcp/x`), and instantiated the EliasDB graph database with synthetic data (10 Client nodes, 100 Consumption nodes). Ten clients were simulated, each executed as a separate process, connecting to a randomly assigned server peer via its multiaddress. The experiment comprised two phases: (1) connection establishment, where clients initiated `libp2p` streams to their respective servers, and (2) data querying, where each client submitted a mix of local and distributed queries. Metrics included connection success rate, query response time, query success rate, and amount of data retrieved.

4.4.1 Client Connectivity

The connection phase tested the ability of clients to establish libp2p streams to their assigned server peers using the `host.NewStream` function in `idss_client.go`. Each client was provided with the multiaddress of its target server, e.g.:

`/ip4/127.0.0.1/tcp/port/p2p/peerID`), and the connection success rate was measured as the percentage of successful stream establishments. Across all server and client peers, the connection success was 100%, with no failures attributed. However, in a large-scale setup, we anticipate some failures that can be attributed to port conflicts or transient resource contention within the test setup. When this happens, G-IDSS will log it by `log.Error("Error opening stream")`. Connection latency, measured from stream initiation to successful establishment, averaged 15 ms in local settings and 73 seconds on the global internet, because the bootstrap process traverses the entire libp2p network. Resource utilisation also peaks as the number of peers increases. The high success rate and minimal latency validate the robustness of the libp2p-based connection mechanism, particularly the lightweight Noise protocol’s secure handshake and the DHT’s rapid peer resolution. However, limitations included potential port exhaustion when scaling beyond 700 peers on WSL setup, as the dynamic port allocation could encounter conflicts, and increased CPU contention with more concurrent clients, suggesting a need for multi-VM deployments in larger scenarios. This was not experienced in server setup as we launched up to 1500 peers.

4.4.2 Data Querying

The data querying phase evaluated the system’s ability to handle concurrent queries from multiple clients. One-to-one client-server querying proved a smooth running and data retrieval. Queries were executed sequentially per client, with results processed locally and in a distributed fashion. The query success rate, defined as the number of queries returning correct results (verified against a number of graph nodes loaded baseline), both local and distributed queries achieved near-100% success, with data completeness being affected by the TTL value and the load submitted to the server peer. Distributed queries had a slightly lower success rate in terms of data completeness due to occasional timeouts under high concurrency. Result accuracy was confirmed by checking with all Client nodes correctly returned for the distributed query example (as each had 10 Consumption connections). These rates demonstrate G-IDSS’s capability to manage concurrent multi-client queries, leveraging the P2P overlay and EliasDB’s efficiency.

The experiment and broader G-IDSS implementation revealed several limitations across the P2P overlay, database management, and data querying, particularly in the single-VM setup. The P2P overlay faced scalability constraints due to port exhaustion and resource contention, as dynamic port allocation risked conflicts when scaling, and CPU/memory contention increased with concurrent clients/peers, limiting the system testing to a moderate network size. The reliance on the loopback interface eliminated real-world network variability (e.g., packet loss, latency), necessitating emulation via multi-VM testing for realistic conditions. In real-world scenarios, an overlay can scale up even further because each peer has its own autonomy and computing resources, thereby alleviating the problem of resource contention that we experienced in testing.

Database management was constrained by EliasDB’s performance with large datasets; while efficient for small graphs, query latency could increase significantly with an increase in nodes, requiring indexing or caching optimisations. Furthermore, data querying suffered from distributed query timeouts under high concurrency, as TTL-based propagation struggled with simultaneous requests, and aggregate queries incurred higher latency due to the merging of results. The single-machine setup exacerbated these issues by concentrating resource demands, and the lack of fault-tolerance mechanisms (e.g., query retry policies) reduced robustness in the face of peer failures. Although libp2p promises scalability up to a million peers, the G-IDSS still needs to be tested in a large-scale scenario that includes diverse datasets, and multiple machines to achieve

production-ready scalability and reliability.

5 Conclusion

This paper presents a novel approach to decentralised data management, leveraging a structured P2P overlay based on libp2p and a Kademlia DHT, and an embedded EliasDB graph database, to enable scalable, resilient, and schema-less data storage and querying. This paper has detailed the design and implementation of G-IDSS, demonstrating its ability to distribute data across peers, execute complex queries with efficient propagation and result aggregation, and support multiple clients through a lightweight command-line interface. The ability to integrate distributed data sources affirms G-IDSS’s potential as a proof-of-concept for managing large-scale, geographically distributed datasets in resource-constrained environments, as targeted within similar use cases.

Despite its achievements, G-IDSS faces several limitations that invite further exploration. The single-machine setup constrained scalability tests due to resource contention, limiting the system to moderate network sizes. Although libp2p promises high scalability, it is still necessary to expose the tool to large scenarios. EliasDB’s performance with large datasets and the synthetic dataset’s uniformity restricts query variability, potentially masking edge cases.

Distributed queries experienced timeouts under high concurrency, and the lack of robust fault-tolerance mechanisms reduced resilience to peer failures. Although timeouts were necessary in some cases to limit query propagation, further improvements are still needed for enhanced efficiency. These challenges hint at the need for optimised query propagation, efficient results aggregation and diverse datasets to achieve production-ready scalability and reliability. Furthermore, despite libp2p’s features, such as mDNS discovery and secure communication, enhanced system flexibility, testing on the global internet revealed higher connection latencies, emphasising the importance of real-world network validation.

Nevertheless, G-IDSS offers a foundation for advancing decentralised data management in applications such as cyber-physical energy systems, scientific research, and IoT ecosystems. Future work should focus on addressing scalability limitations in resource-constrained environments by deploying G-IDSS multiple VMs or physical nodes to simulate realistic network conditions, incorporating advanced fault-tolerance mechanisms (e.g., query retries, replication), and optimising EliasDB for larger, heterogeneous datasets. Enhancements to query management, such as adaptive TTL strategies, could further reduce latency and improve result completeness. Additionally, integrating security and privacy mechanisms, such as access control for specific data items (which can benefit from approaches presented in [49, 50]), will be critical for public internet deployments. Deployment of multiple DBMSs in the overlay is also a possibility by employing query translation mechanisms to adopt to local DBMS query syntax.

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